

**THE VALUE OF LIFE IN THE SHORT STORY "THE LAST LEAF" BY
O'HENRY**

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Abstract This article includes the short plot and basic ideas dealing with human life and its value that written in the short story "The Last Leaf" by O'Henry.

Key words: hopefullness, appreciation, value, human sacrifice,disease

O'Henry is a pen name of William Sydney Porter . He was famous writer as described "the king of short-stories" by critics. He began writing stories when he was in prison. "The Last Leaf" appeared first on October 15 , 1905. It was published in the collection "The Trimmed Lamp and Other Stories" in 1907. He is the writer of many famous stories some of which are included in the collection ,such as "The Pendulum", "The Purple Dress", "The Guilty Party" and so on. O'Henry managed to write and publish such stories in spite of some terrible situations which occurred in New York¹.

"The Last Leaf" is one of the stories that were written skilfully . The important point is that, we can take sententious lesson from it. It teaches us the appreciation of life, living thankfully, enjoying every moment that is given to us and not belittling it. Having quite a lot of meaning, this short story differs from the others considerably, and can attract everyone, even they are not keen on reading. It is showed as a direction for life. As Albert Einstein said:" Life is riding a bycycle. To keep your balance, you must keep moving"².

Generally, in this short story, pneumonia which was a disease widely spread in Greenwich is showed as a main cause to all incidents. One of two friends called

¹ https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Panic_of_1907

² <https://www.wionews.com/trending/albert-einstein-birthday-know-motivational-quotes-by-him-facts-inventions-discoveries-and-share-wishes-571797/amp>

Johnsy caught this illness earlier that lead the woman almost to die thereafter . Woman thought that, her life was related to a tree shedding its leaves day by day , and her life was being finished like leaves by an illness. Doctor said that, all things as to getting well is up to hopefulness.

*"She has a very small chance. She has a chance, if she wants to live. If people do not want to live, I cannot do much for them"*³

That's why Johnsy's friend Sue always tries to make her happy and confident. Unfortunately, all of Johnsy's beliefs were depended on that tree and its last leaf that decides whether her life goes on or not. Because of a man who had not had a chance to show his ability but dreamed to do so, could save the woman from death. The only thing he did was painting a picture which give her a hope of living. Woman was waiting for her end looking at the leaf which was alone . But her friend Sue found a solution by telling their neighbour to draw a picture in which the tree opposite to the wall and the last leaf – the last hope of Johnsy. Mr. Behrman managed this, the first time he had an opportunity to carry out a crucial thing that represents his greatness. By watching the leaf standing in the same state and not being separated from the tree, Johnsy come back to life, she realized the value of it. She considered herself as a mad person who tied life to just a leaf. Unfortunately, after some time, Mr.Behrman was swallowed by pneumonia , he died rescuing one's soul.

Life is such a thing that given us by Allah as the only chance. We do not have any opportunity to change its duration. It is not in the hands of us or not related to little things as mentioned in the story:

“What? Are there such fools? Do people die because leaves drop off a tree?”

*"What? Are there such fools? Do people die because leaves drop off a tree?"*⁴

But we can choose how we live , full of hope or just being careless. Existence is precious, because it will never come back, one who realized its significance, tries to

³ <https://learningenglish.voanews.com/amp/the-last-leaf-by-o-henry/4480411.html>

⁴ <https://learningenglish.voanews.com/amp/the-last-leaf-by-o-henry/4480411.html>

do everything so as not to lose any moment, no one will be awarded one more time. Feelings about preciousness of life is explained differently in the story "Love of Life" by Jack London.

" He, as a man , no longer strove. It was the life in him, unwilling to die, that drow him on". [Jack London-11]

"He as a man, no longer strove. It was the life in him, unwilling to die, that drow him on".⁵

Main hero of this story unlike to "The Last Leaf" does not give up his expectation of life and does his best in order to live further being careless about wealth which have been their purpose at first.

AS to historical times, human sacrifice was considered as an honor in some ancient societies like Mayans. Comparing with today's world, nowadays the young are aslo negligent about their life, by reason of some harmful opinions that spread intentionally. A few of them are sacrificing themselves owing to lack of knowledge about the worthiness of life, and it is easy for them to give up when facing particular problems which seem to be never solved. Before deciding about one's life a person should ask one thing from himself or herself: "Is my judgement true ?", "Why was I given the opportunity to live", "Will not I regret?" The issue described in the short story is a foremost matter and intrigues everyone throughout the world. That's why it has had millions of readers for a century.

Conclusion. "The Last Leaf " by O'Henry helps us to understand better worth of life. Readers can take an important lesson about valuing their existence. Even today, this short story is being read by a great number of people because of its significance that raised one of the most crucial topics .

THE LIST OF THE USED LITERATURE

⁵ <https://learningenglish.voanews.com/amp/love-of-life-by-jack-london-part-one/4656684.html>

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